

An Enhanced Ant Colony Optimization (ACO) Methodology for Fuel Lattice Design Optimization

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ABSTRACT

This study details an enhanced ant colony optimization (ACO) methodology tailored for the complex, discrete problem of nuclear fuel lattice optimization. Standard ACO algorithms applied to lattice design often suffer from premature convergence to local optima. To overcome this, our enhanced ACO introduces several key improvements: a random ant selection mechanism based on a diminishing trigger threshold, and a dynamic pheromone reinforcement strategy with adaptive upper and lower bounds. This paper focuses on the algorithm's architecture, its operational parameters, and its search behavior. We present a detailed convergence analysis, showing the fitness function (Lattice Power Peaking Factor, PPF) exhibits a rapid improvement within the initial 30 generations, followed by stable convergence, achieving a ~2.8% reduction in PPF. Furthermore, we visualize the pheromone map evolution over 50 iterations, demonstrating the algorithm's robust mechanism for identifying and reinforcing optimal placement locations. A 17×17 PWR-type lattice optimization problem is used as a test case to validate the methodology and analyze its convergence characteristics. The results confirm the enhanced ACO is a stable and effective tool for this class of optimization problem.

Keywords: ant colony optimization, lattice design, optimization, convergence analysis

1. INTRODUCTION

The design of nuclear fuel lattices involves optimizing the placement of fuel rods with varying enrichments and burnable absorbers to ensure operational safety and economic efficiency. A primary objective is the minimization of the local power peaking factor (PPF), which is critical in modern compact cores like those in Small Modular Reactors (SMRs) [1, 2]. Gadolinium-based burnable absorbers (Gd_2O_3) are commonly used to control excess reactivity and flatten the power distribution [3]. Due to the discrete and highly combinatorial nature of rod placement, metaheuristic optimization algorithms are well-suited for this task.

While genetic algorithms (GA) and simulated annealing (SA) have seen wide application, Ant Colony Optimization (ACO) has also been utilized for lattice design [4, 5]. However, standard ACO is known to be susceptible to early convergence toward local solutions. Kishi and Kitada incorporated a mutation concept from GAs into ACO to improve its ability to escape local minima [6]. This indicates a need for more robust ACO methodologies tailored to the complex problem of fuel lattice optimization.

This study details the development and behavior of an enhanced ACO algorithm designed to improve search-space exploration and convergence speed. We analyze its convergence characteristics and the evolution of its search-guiding pheromones. While this methodology is applied to a representative PWR-type SMR lattice problem to demonstrate its effectiveness in minimizing the Lattice Power Peaking Factor (PPF), the primary focus of this paper is the algorithmic enhancements and their performance, rather than a full-scale core design verification.

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2. METHODOLOGY

2.1. The Lattice Optimization Problem (Test Case)

To validate the ACO methodology, a representative optimization problem was defined. The test case utilizes a 17×17 PWR-type fuel assembly lattice with 24 guide tubes, a central instrument tube, and a U-235 enrichment of 4.5 w/o. The objective is to find the optimal placement for 20 gadolinia-bearing fuel rods to minimize the lattice PPF.

Based on preliminary analysis (details omitted for brevity), a two-group gadolinia concentration distribution was established for the 20 Gd rods: 12 rods with 7.0 wt% C_{Gd} and 8 rods with 3.25 wt% C_{Gd} . The optimization problem is thus to assign these 20 rods to the 39 available symmetric positions (see Fig. 2) to find the configuration with the lowest PPF. The fitness function (PPF) for each configuration is evaluated using the CASMO-5 lattice physics code [7].

2.2. Enhanced Ant Colony Optimization Algorithm

To identify the optimal lattice design, this study employs an enhanced ACO algorithm (*Figure 1*). A one-eighth symmetry (*Figure 2*) is adopted. In the initial stage, the pheromone concentration τ_0 at all legal coordinates is set to a constant. Each ant selects positions based on a probabilistic model or randomly, which are then mirrored to the full lattice.

Figure 1. Ant Colony Optimization calculation procedure.

Figure 2. Fuel lattice configuration with one-eighth symmetry.

The probability p_i for placing a Gd rod at position i is defined as:

$$p_i = \frac{\tau_i^\alpha \cdot \eta_i^\beta}{\sum_{j \in \text{unselected}} \tau_j^\alpha \cdot \eta_j^\beta} \quad (1)$$

where τ_i is the pheromone value and η_i is the heuristic value, defined as the PPF at each position without gadolinium. The parameters α and β represent the relative influence of pheromone and heuristic information, respectively. The evaporation factor ρ ($0 < \rho < 1$) regulates the decay rate of accumulated pheromones during the global update phase. A higher ρ value enhances exploration by accelerating pheromone decay, whereas a smaller ρ prioritizes exploitation by preserving historical search trajectories.

Following extensive parametric sensitivity tests (covering $\alpha = 1.0\text{--}2.0$, $\beta = 2.0\text{--}5.0$, $\rho = 0.1\text{--}0.5$), the results presented in this study utilize a robust parameter set: $\alpha = 2.0$, $\beta = 2.0$, $\rho = 0.2$.

The fitness function, to be minimized, is defined as:

$$\text{Fitness} = \max(P) \quad (2)$$

To prevent premature convergence, several enhancements are introduced:

1. **Random Ant Selection:** A trigger threshold ϵ is defined. Before selecting a position, an ant generates a random number R . If $R \geq \epsilon$, the position is selected via Eq. (1); otherwise, the position is chosen randomly. The threshold ϵ_G for the G -th generation decreases over time:

$$\epsilon_G = \epsilon_0 \cdot \left(1 - \frac{G - 1}{G_{\max}}\right) \quad (3)$$

where ϵ_0 is 0.1 and G_{\max} is 150.

2. **Dynamic Pheromone Reinforcement:** After each iteration, the j solutions with the lowest fitness values are selected for reinforcement. The reinforcement amount $\Delta\tau$ for the j -th ranked ant is:

$$\tau_i^{(G+1)} = (1 - \rho)\tau_i^{(G)} + \sum_{j=1}^k \Delta\tau_{i,j}^{(G+1)} \quad (4)$$

where ρ is the evaporation factor ($0 < \rho < 1$), which controls pheromone decay to avoid unlimited accumulation and premature convergence.

$$\Delta\tau_{j,G+1} = \frac{Q_{max}}{\text{Fitness}(j)} \cdot RF \quad (5)$$

$$Q_{max} = \frac{\text{Fitness}(\text{best}, G)}{\Delta\tau_{max}} \quad (6)$$

$$\Delta\tau_{max} = \rho \cdot (-2.25 \cdot \rho + 2.225) \quad (7)$$

The maximum pheromone increment is limited by $\Delta\tau_{max} = \rho \cdot (-2.25 \cdot \rho + 2.225)$, where ρ is the evaporation rate. This formulation scales the allowable update according to ρ , such that higher evaporation reduces the increment while lower evaporation permits stronger reinforcement.

$$RF = \begin{cases} 1, & j = 1 \\ 3, & j \neq 1 \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

In each iteration, at most three and at least one of the best-ranked solutions are selected for reinforcement. This prevents pheromone accumulation from being overly concentrated on the Gd rod configuration of a single best solution and enhances positional diversity.

$$j_B = NINT \left[j_{B-1} \cdot \left(1 - \frac{G-1}{G_{max}} \right) \right] \quad (9)$$

- Adaptive Pheromone Bounds:** Upper (5.0) and lower (0.1) bounds are set for τ_i . The lower bound is halved every 15 iterations to enhance search efficiency.

To maintain numerical stability, pheromone values are bounded within [0.1, 5.0], preventing over-concentration and preserving exploration capability.

3. ALGORITHM PERFORMANCE AND CONVERGENCE ANALYSIS

This section analyzes the search behavior and convergence characteristics of the enhanced ACO algorithm under the fixed settings (150 generations, 15 ants, $\alpha = 2.0$, $\beta = 2.0$, $\rho = 0.2$).

3.1. Fitness Function (PPF) Convergence

Figure 3 illustrates the convergence characteristics of the enhanced ACO. Figure 3(a) presents the best fitness (PPF) found in each generation, showing a typical “rapid improvement – stable exploration” behavior. The PPF decreases quickly during the first 30 generations and then exhibits minor oscillations, indicating continued exploration while avoiding stagnation.

Figure 3(b) shows the global best fitness up to each generation. A rapid monotonic decrease is observed in the early stage, followed by complete stabilization at the final optimal value of 1.096. The algorithm completes its primary improvement within approximately 30 generations, achieving a total PPF reduction of ~2.8%.

The generation limit $G_{max} = 150$ was designated as a conservative upper bound rather than an empirically optimized value. Since the ACO parameters (α , β , ρ) were evaluated within predefined ranges, a sufficiently high generation cap was adopted to ensure stable convergence across diverse

parameter combinations. A complete optimization run (150 generations with 15 ants each) requires approximately 3 hours, with the computational cost being primarily dominated by CASMO-5 lattice physics evaluations. Increasing G_{max} significantly would proportionally increase computational time without yielding further improvement in the final solution.

To further assess the contribution of the proposed exploration mechanism, an additional calculation was performed using the same parameter set ($\alpha = 2.0$, $\beta = 2.0$, $\rho = 0.2$) with $\varepsilon_0 = 0$, i.e., without random ant selection. The corresponding convergence curve is included in Figure 3(b).

As shown, although the standard ACO ($\varepsilon_0 = 0$) exhibits slightly faster initial convergence, it stabilizes at a higher final PPF. In contrast, the enhanced ACO maintains continued exploration in early generations and ultimately achieves a lower global best PPF. This comparison clearly demonstrates that the diminishing random selection mechanism effectively mitigates premature convergence and improves final solution quality.

Figure 3. Convergence history of the fitness function (PPF) over 150 generations: (a) Best fitness per generation, showing search dynamics, and (b) Comparison of global best fitness convergence between the enhanced ACO ($\varepsilon_0 \neq 0$) and the standard ACO ($\varepsilon_0 = 0$)

3.2. Robustness and Sensitivity to Random Seed

Since the ACO algorithm is inherently stochastic, its robustness was evaluated by performing ten independent runs using different random seeds. The same parameter set ($\alpha = 2.0$, $\beta = 2.0$, $\rho = 0.2$) was used for all runs.

The resulting best fitness values (PPF) from ten independent trials ranged from 1.096 to 1.104, with an ensemble average of 1.100. The relative variation across these runs is within 0.73%, demonstrating that the algorithm consistently converges to high-quality solutions with minimal sensitivity to stochastic initialization.

These results confirm that the proposed enhanced ACO algorithm is robust and exhibits low sensitivity to random initialization, demonstrating reliable optimization performance.

3.3. Pheromone Map Evolution

To visualize the algorithm's search behavior, the pheromone distributions on the lattice coordinates were examined at different iteration steps (Figure 4).

- Gen 1 (Figure 4a): The pheromones are uniformly distributed, representing the initial random search phase.

- Gen 5 (Figure 4b): A preliminary aggregation of pheromones appears on coordinates 6, 14, 21, 36, and 37, indicating initial preferences are forming.
- Gen 10 (Figure 4c): The concentration becomes more obvious, strengthening on high-quality paths (e.g., 6, 14, 33, 34, 36).
- Gen 50 (Figure 4d): The pheromone map stabilizes and converges, with the highest concentrations on a few key coordinates (6, 14, 21, 38).

This evolution clearly shows the algorithm successfully converging. The evaporation mechanism functions correctly, as non-optimal positions decay towards the lower bound (0.0125). The converged map suggests that placing rods at coordinates 6, 14, 21, and 38 (and their symmetric equivalents) is key to minimizing the PPF.

Figure 4. Pheromone map evolution at (a) 1st, (b) 5th, (c) 10th, and (d) 50th generations.

3.4. Optimized Lattice Configuration

The converged solution from the ACO algorithm ("Lattice 3") is shown in Figure 5, compared to a baseline design ("Lattice 2") which used a simple placement for the same rods, and an initial single-group design ("Lattice 1"). The ACO algorithm relocated the lower-concentration (3.25 %) Gd rods closer to the center compared to the baseline. The numerical labels shown in Figure 5 denote different rod types, as specified in the figure caption.

The neutronic performance of this configuration (Figure 6) validates the algorithm's success. The K_{inf} curves (Figure 6a) are nearly identical, confirming the optimization did not distort the reactivity profile. However, the lattice PPF (Figure 6b) shows a clear improvement. The ACO-optimized Lattice 3 maintains the lowest PPF throughout the burnup cycle and, crucially, eliminates the temporary PPF rise seen in the baseline design near 10 GWd/MTU. This confirms the converged solution is not just mathematically optimal but also neutronically superior.

Figure 5. (a) Initial design (Lattice 1), (b) Two-group C_{Gd} distribution baseline (Lattice 2), and (c) ACO-optimized design (Lattice 3). Cell numbering legend: 0 – Guide tube or instrument tube; 1 – Standard UO_2 fuel rod; 2 – Single-type gadolinia rod; 3 and 4 – Two gadolinia rod types whose average concentration equals that of type 2.

Figure 6. Fuel-lattice results for the designs: (a) K_{inf} vs. burnup, and (b) power-peaking factor.

4. CONCLUSIONS

This study successfully developed and detailed an enhanced Ant Colony Optimization (ACO) algorithm for the optimization of nuclear fuel lattices. By introducing a random ant selection

mechanism based on a diminishing threshold and a dynamic, bounded pheromone reinforcement strategy, the algorithm effectively navigates the complex, discrete search space to find robust solutions.

Analysis of the algorithm's performance demonstrated rapid and stable convergence, achieving a 2.8% reduction in the Lattice Power Peaking Factor (PPF) within 30 generations. Visualization of the pheromone maps confirmed the algorithm's effectiveness in identifying and reinforcing optimal rod placements, providing a clear path to convergence.

By focusing on the methodology and its convergence behavior, this work provides a robust and validated optimization tool for the general problem of nuclear fuel lattice design. The results from the test case confirm that the optimized configuration is neutronicallly superior to a baseline design, validating the algorithm's practical effectiveness.

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